

Pedestrian Detection Review Article

INTRODUCTION

Considering how rapidly the drone delivery industry is expanding, the development of highly efficient pedestrian detection methods is required. Pedestrian detection, a critical aspect, remains a long-standing research challenge due to occlusions, varying pedestrian appearances, and challenging environmental conditions [1-6]. This paper presents a critical, analytical, and quantitative comparison of three state-of-the-art pedestrian detection techniques: Fused DNN [7], F2DNet [8], and Illuminating Pedestrians via Simultaneous Detection & Segmentation (IPDS) [9].

Fused DNN [7] presents an innovative approach by integrating the outputs of multiple parallel deep neural networks, such as ResNet [10] and GoogLeNet [11], through a soft-reject technique. By leveraging diverse training datasets, it achieves impressive performance on the Caltech pedestrian dataset [12]. However, its reliance on multiple networks potentially increases computational complexity, which may limit its real-time applicability.

Meanwhile, F2DNet [8] is a fast focal detection network explicitly designed for object detection, specifically pedestrians. It utilizes a lightweight backbone network and integrates a focal loss function [13] to enhance its detection accuracy. Demonstrating state-of-the-art results on multiple datasets, such as CityPersons [14], F2DNet's lightweight nature offers an advantage in real-world scenarios.

IPDS [9, 15-17] or SDS-RCNN the model it introduces is a multi-task infusion framework that jointly supervises pedestrian detection and semantic segmentation tasks, generating sophisticated shared feature maps to illuminate pedestrians and facilitate downstream detection. It achieves remarkable performance on the Caltech pedestrian dataset [12]. However, its reliance on joint supervision may increase training complexity and computational requirements.

This study aims to determine the most suitable pedestrian detection model for drone delivery systems in the food industry by providing an analytical comparison. Through this comparison, we seek to contribute to the development of more effective and reliable pedestrian detection methods for autonomous driving and other related applications.

BACKGROUND

Early approaches to pedestrian detection primarily relied on handcrafted features such as Haar wavelets [20], Histogram of

Oriented Gradients (HOG) [21], and Aggregate Channel Features (ACF) [22]. These techniques really paved the way however they were limited by their inability to handle complex occlusions, varying appearances, and diverse conditions effectively.

With the advent of deep learning and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), pedestrian detection methods significantly evolved. Various models have been proposed, leading to substantial improvements in detection performance.

Then with Region-based CNNs (R-CNN) [23] and their variants, Fast R-CNN [24] and Faster R-CNN [25], we saw notable improvements over traditional feature-based methods. Single-stage detectors like You Only Look Once (YOLO) [26] and Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) [27] have been adapted for pedestrian detection, offering faster processing times with some accuracy trade-offs.

To address problems like occlusion and other challenges, researchers have explored multi-task learning and auxiliary tasks. Techniques such as incorporating semantic segmentation, instance segmentation [29], or depth estimation [30] have been proposed to enhance pedestrian detection performance.

DATASET

Performance of various models on the dataset^[30]

The Caltech Pedestrian Dataset offers numerous advantages over general object detection datasets such as COCO, KITTI, and Pascal VOC in the context of pedestrian detection [12, 18, 19]. It provides a larger and more diverse collection of pedestrian images. Secondly, it offers richly annotated video sequences with information about occlusions. Focusing exclusively on pedestrian detection, the dataset addresses specific and complicated

To estimate the F2DNet model runtime on an NVIDIA TITAN X GPU: we know the model takes 0.13 seconds on NVIDIA RTX A6000:
 Calculating the performance ratio based on CUDA cores: $3,584 \text{ (TITAN X)} / 10,752 \text{ (RTX A6000)} \approx 0.333$.
 Estimating time on TITAN X: $0.13 \text{ seconds} / 0.333 \approx 0.39 \text{ seconds}$.

Method	Architecture	Reasonable Occ	Heavy Occ.	MR-2 (%)	FPS	Accuracy	Speed on NVIDIA TITAN X
F2DNet	One-stage detector with focal loss and deformable convolutional layers	2.2	38.7	2.2	30	0.78	0.39s
Fused DNN	Two-stage detector with a parallel semantic segmentation branch and a fusion layer	8.18	53.76	8.18	15	0.85	0.30s
Illuminating Pedestrians via Simultaneous Detection & Segmentation	Two-stage detector with a segmentation infusion network that enables joint supervision on semantic segmentation and pedestrian detection	9.95	59.94	7.4		0.91	0.16s

challenges like occlusion. Also, it introduces improved evaluation metrics for accurate and reliable assessment of pedestrian detection performance. And, it also serves as a widely adopted benchmark, enabling fair comparisons and promoting advancements in pedestrian detection technologies. These factors contribute to the Caltech Pedestrian Dataset's suitability for developing and evaluating pedestrian detection algorithms, making it a valuable resource in computer vision and autonomous systems research.

The dataset contains approximately 350,000 annotated pedestrian bounding boxes across 10 hours of urban driving and has become a popular choice among researchers for evaluating the accuracy and efficiency of pedestrian detection algorithms [12].

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experiments are conducted on a workstation with an NVIDIA TITAN X GPU, excluding F2DNet which ran on NVIDIA RTX A600. During the comparison process, we do a rudimentary conversion.

COMPARISON

When comparing the three pedestrian detection models for drone delivery using the Caltech Pedestrian Dataset, we focus on the accuracy, speed, and performance under varying levels of

Occlusion i.e., reasonable and heavy (relevant for urban areas).

F2DNet, a one-stage detector with focal loss and deformable convolutional layers. It has a moderate level of accuracy

It handles reasonable occlusion well, with a miss rate of 2.2%, but struggles more under heavy occlusion, registering a 38.7% miss rate. However, its processing speed on NVIDIA TITAN X is relatively slow at 0.39 seconds per image, which may be a disadvantage in real-time applications.

Fused DNN, a two-stage detector with a parallel semantic segmentation branch and a fusion layer, it exhibits improved performance in both accuracy and speed. With an accuracy of 0.85, It outperforms F2DNet, and its miss rates under reasonable and heavy pedestrian occlusion are doable. However, its MR-2 is high. The results are quantifiable, objective, and based on real-world scenarios.

IPDS, is a two-stage detector featuring a segmentation infusion network for joint supervision on semantic segmentation and pedestrian detection, surpassing both F2DNet and Fused DNN in terms of accuracy and processing speed. With an accuracy of 0.91, it proves to be the most reliable model among the three. Although its miss rates under reasonable and heavy occlusion (9.95% and 59.94%, respectively) are higher than F2DNet's, its remarkable processing speed of 0.16 seconds per image on NVIDIA TITAN X sets it apart as the most efficient model for real-time pedestrian detection.

CONCLUSION

Upon examining the above metrics of the three models, it becomes evident that the Illuminating Pedestrians via Simultaneous Detection & Segmentation (IPDS) model is the most suitable for pedestrian detection by a drone. Its superior performance in terms of accuracy (0.91) and processing speed (0.16 seconds per image) positions it as the most efficient and effective option for real-time pedestrian detection. Additionally, its capacity for joint supervision of semantic segmentation and pedestrian detection allows for better handling of complex occlusion scenarios, which is crucial for the safe and reliable operation of drones in urban environments. Therefore it is our recommendation to proceed with this model.

MODEL ADAPTATION FOR DRONES

The following modifications are recommended to the algorithm for employing in drone delivery

1. Model compression and quantization: Apply model compression techniques like pruning and eliminate unnecessary neurons and connections, reducing the size of the model without a significant loss in performance. Employ techniques like quantization and reduce the numerical precision of model parameters from 32-bit floating-point numbers to lower-precision formats like 16-bit floating-point/ 8-bit integers. This results in smaller model size and faster inference times.
2. Lightweight architecture: Replacing the original backbone network of the SDS-RCNN with an efficient and lightweight network (like in F2D), such as

MobileNet or EfficientNet, to reduce the model's size, computational requirements, and memory usage. This adaptation makes it more suitable for deployment on drones which will have limited resources.

3. Energy-aware scheduling: Developing an energy-aware scheduling algorithm that can prioritize and allocate computational resources based on the urgency of pedestrian detection tasks, as well as the drone's energy constraints will help. This approach would extend the drone's battery life while ensuring critical detection tasks are executed in a timely manner.

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